

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

Package of Dissemination Materials 4

Work Package 7, Deliverable D7.9

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Package of Dissemination Materials 4

Work package 7, Deliverable D7.9

Please refer to this report as follows:

Vuckovic, M., Kozłowska, A. (2025). Package of Dissemination Materials 4. Deliverable D7.9 of the Horizon Europe project GREENGAGE.

Project information	
Project name:	GREENGAGE – Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal
Grant Agreement No.	101086530
Start date:	01/01/2023
Duration:	36 months
Coordinator:	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology Giefinggasse 4, 1210 Vienna, Austria
Contact:	Jan Peters-Anders, Research Engineer
	Funded by the European Union GA n° 101086530.
Deliverable details	
Description:	This document presents the third version of the existing digital assets as well as additional material to be used within the GREENGAGE project for promotional and visibility purposes: A promotional A4 poster and an informational leaflet depicting the essential aspects of the project, as well as informational flyers and a roll-up banner.
Version:	Final
Dissemination level:	PU (Public)
Due date:	31/12/2025
Submission:	23/12/2025
Lead:	VRVis Zentrum für Virtual Reality und Visualisierung Forschungs-GmbH
Author(s):	Vuckovic, M. (VRVis Zentrum für Virtual Reality und Visualisierung Forschungs-GmbH), Austria Kozłowska, A. (Austrian Institute of Technology), Austria

Legal Disclaimer

All information in this document is provided "as is" and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user, therefore, uses the information at its sole risk and liability. For the avoidance of all doubts, the European Commission has no liability in respect of this document, which is merely representing the authors' view.

Users wishing to reuse material from this work that is attributed to a third party, such as tables, figures or images, are responsible for determining whether permission is needed for that reuse and for obtaining permission from the copyright holder. The risk of claims resulting from infringement of any third party-owned component in the work rests solely with the user.

© 2025 by REENGAGE Consortium

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Table of Contents

Content

1	REENGAGE summary.....	4
2	Introduction.....	5
3	Description of Dissemination Materials.....	6
3.1	A4 Poster.....	6
3.2	Foldable leaflet.....	8
3.3	REENGAGE Observatories Factsheet.....	12
3.4	Roll-Up Banner.....	14
3.5	T-Shirt Design.....	18

List of Figures

Figure 1:	Structure of project REENGAGE.....	4
Figure 2:	Promotional A4 poster.....	6
Figure 3:	Promotional A4 poster in Italian language.....	7
Figure 4:	Promotional A4 poster in Dutch language.....	8
Figure 5:	Promotional leaflet: front page.....	9
Figure 6:	Promotional leaflet: rear page.....	10
Figure 7:	Promotional leaflet in Italian language: front page.....	10
Figure 8:	Promotional leaflet in Italian language: rear page.....	11
Figure 9:	Promotional leaflet in Dutch language: front page.....	11
Figure 10:	Promotional leaflet in Dutch language: rear page.....	12
Figure 11:	Citizen Observatories Factsheet Booklet: pages 1 - 4 of the PDF booklet.....	13
Figure 12:	Citizen Observatories Factsheet Booklet: pages 5 - 8 of the PDF booklet.....	14
Figure 13:	Promotional roll-up banner.....	15
Figure 14:	Promotional roll-up banner in Italian language.....	16
Figure 15:	Promotional roll-up banner in Dutch language.....	17
Figure 16:	T-shirt design that features the REENGAGE logo and relevant funding information.....	18

Executive summary (publishable)

This document presents the fourth version of the WP7 GREENGAGE deliverable D7.6 - *Package of dissemination materials 1*. The first version was delivered in M6, in which two digital assets were presented: A promotional A4 poster and an informational leaflet depicting the essential aspects of the project. The second version was delivered in M13, in which an informational flyer introducing each of the Pilots, their individual background information, and their use cases within the scope of Citizen Observatories was delivered, in addition to the original assets that were revised to allow for better legibility and enhanced clarity of the communicated information. The third version was delivered in M24 and included a promotional roll-up banner, along with revisions to previously developed materials.

The current version provides a list of existing and additional digital assets to be used for promotional and visibility purposes: a T-shirt design used for Datathons and Ideathons.

All these assets will be made readily available on the GREENGAGE website for download.

Related documents

All GREENGAGE deliverables that are related to this document are listed below and are available at the GREENGAGE website <https://www.greengage-project.eu/knowledge-base/deliverables/>.

GREENGAGE Deliverable D7.1 Plan for the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results 1

GREENGAGE Deliverable D7.2 Plan for the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results 2

GREENGAGE Deliverable D7.4 Project Identity and Branding

GREENGAGE Deliverable D7.5 Project Website and Social Media Platforms

GREENGAGE Deliverable D7.6 Package of Dissemination Materials 1

GREENGAGE Deliverable D7.7 Package of Dissemination Materials 2

GREENGAGE Deliverable D7.8 Package of Dissemination Materials 3

1 GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aimed to promote innovative governance processes, and tried to help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project leveraged citizens' participation and equipped them with innovative digital solutions that shall transform citizen's engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, the aim was to inspire citizens to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The idea was to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This was facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories were and are a place where pilot cities co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up processes with top-down perspectives. This provides the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aimed to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The Citizens Observatory campaigns were deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano Valley (Italy), Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aimed to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which should complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE.

2 Introduction

Dissemination and promotional materials play a crucial role in enhancing visibility and building awareness of the GREENGAGE project, ultimately contributing to the overall success and recognition of the project. Therefore, this deliverable and its integral parts are completely aligned with the deliverable D7.1 - *Plan for the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results 1* - a comprehensive plan outlining GREENGAGE's dissemination and communication strategy, initially published in M3 and subsequently updated (D7.2 - *Plan for the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results 2*).

In the conceptualization phase of these materials, we have drawn from established visual design principles to achieve both visual attractiveness and clarity in conveying desired information. We have considered the principles of accessible visual design, whereby we aimed for legibility and simplicity of the adopted design. These relate to the careful use of typefaces with clear lines and shapes, large enough font size for text that promotes comfortable reading, clean structure, and avoidance of visual clutter. Additionally, colour scheme and other design-related elements are adopted from the project logo and documentation templates.

A PDF and a JPG copy of these materials, depending on the nature of the design asset, are made available for a free download from the GREENGAGE website under the Knowledge Base menu tab: <https://www.greengage-project.eu/knowledge-base/deliverables/>.

3 Description of Dissemination Materials

3.1 A4 Poster

The digital A4 promotional poster (Figure 2) provides a high-level overview of the GREENGAGE project. Specifically, the poster contains some essential information on the GREENGAGE project, such as its mission and the overview of the GREENGAGE Observatories included in the project. The link leading to the GREENGAGE website and social media accounts are also provided, thus allowing for an increased visibility and promotion of the project and its activities. The poster is also provided in Italian and Dutch languages, effectively eliminating any language barriers for two Italian pilots – Gerace and Turano – and the North Brabant communities (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Revised designs: The second version of the A4 promotional poster featured the adjusted sizing of headings and the main body text for enhanced legibility and visual clarity. Supplementary co-funding initiatives from UK and Switzerland partners were also incorporated. The third version addressed and corrected several wording errors, provided the links to the project’s social media accounts, and included the version in Italian and Dutch languages.

Figure 2: Promotional A4 poster.

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

RAFFORZARE LA GOVERNANCE URBANA PROMUOVENDO LA CO-CREAZIONE BASATA SUI CITTADINI E LA RACCOLTA DATI

OBIETTIVO

Il nostro obiettivo consiste nel migliorare il processo decisionale per la governance delle città, sfruttando al tempo stesso le opportunità sociali e culturali. Promuovendo il coinvolgimento attivo dei cittadini nella raccolta dati e nel processo decisionale urbano attraverso gli Osservatori Cittadini, creiamo una piattaforma affinché i cittadini possano contribuire attivamente al futuro delle loro città.

OSSERVATORI CITTADINI

- Bristol (UK)
- Copenhagen (DK)
- North Brabant (NL)
- Turano – Gerace (IT)

VIENI A TROVARCI ONLINE www.greengage-project.eu

SEGUICI SU www.linkedin.com/company/greengage-project

I PARTNER

 Funded by the European Union

 UK Research and Innovation

Project funded by UK Research and Innovation

Figure 3: Promotional A4 poster in Italian language.

Figure 4: Promotional A4 poster in Dutch language.

3.2 Foldable leaflet

Digital foldable leaflet (Figure 5 and Figure 6) is designed to fit the A4 format, to allow for an effortless adaptation to a printed physical format. This is applicable only when the situation demands it, such as during the participants’ training campaigns, public events and talks, or during conferences and other events. Specifically, the need for physical materials arises from the specific requirements of our innovation pilots and their local communities, considering their preferred methods of processing information and varying levels of technological savviness. This was particularly relevant for our Italian pilots coordinated by I Borghi più belli d’Italia, where the Observers’ preferences leaned towards printed materials, which would result in higher engagement levels. Otherwise, due to the core nature of the GREENGAGE project being considered a “green project”, digital promotional materials would be deemed a preferable alternative to a physical printed form.

Additionally, these materials are also provided in Italian and Dutch languages (Figure 7 - Figure 10), effectively eliminating any language barriers for two Italian pilots – Gerace and Turano – and the North Brabant communities. In contrast, no need for bilingual content emerged from the other pilots thus far.

The leaflet is a two-sided trifold design. The information is presented in a concise manner on the outer and inner side. Along the general information on the project and its activities, the leaflet also depicts integral parts of the GREENGAGE toolbox, where Observers (and other stakeholders) may inform themselves on the considered technologies from the GREENGAGE repertoire.

Revised design: The second version of the A4 leaflet featured the adjusted design with enlarged sizing of headings and the main body text for enhanced legibility and visual clarity. The revised leaflet version integrates several newly designed graphical elements, recognizing that images enhance visual understanding more effectively than plain text. The revised design also included a geographical map marking locations of the pilot areas and their Observatories, thus offering a perspective on the project's scope and scale. Supplementary co-funding initiatives from UK and Switzerland partners were also incorporated. The third version addressed and corrected several wording errors, provided the links to the project's YouTube account, and included the version in Italian and Dutch languages.

Figure 5: Promotional leaflet: front page.

OBJECTIVES

- Raise citizens' awareness, interest, and engagement in urban environmental issues
- Provide scientifically-sound and rigorous methods for citizen understanding of environmental data
- Promote and ensure broader acceptance and implementation rates of data collected by citizens in policy- and decision-making
- Promote the co-creation of data solutions for the urban environment
- Establish synergies among partner cities, with other Citizen Observatories and environmental agencies to exchange best practices, ensure transferability, uptake, and replication of successful Citizen Observatory experiences

GREENGAGE OBSERVATORIES

- Bristol (UK)
- Copenhagen (DK)
- North Brabant (NL)
- Turano (IT)
- Gerace (IT)

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, citizens are inspired to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments within GREENGAGE Observatories.

This enhanced evidence-based information will complement existing data repositories and will be used for smart urban governance including policy evaluation, policymaking and decision-making.

GREENGAGE TOOLBOX

GREENGAGE facilitates the multidisciplinary Citizen Observatories campaigns empowering citizen observers with bespoke tools for environmental monitoring – a GREENGAGE toolbox of technologies.

This "quiver" of technologies consists of existing software and hardware tools of consortium partners promoting data observation, data visualization, information processing and training.

PORTABLE SENSORS

MOBILE APPS

COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENT

VISUALIZATION DASHBOARDS

GEOSPATIAL SOLUTIONS

FOLLOW US!

- [linkedin.com/company/greengage-project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/greengage-project)
- @ GREENGAGE_EU
- @ GREENGAGE-project

Figure 6: Promotional leaflet: rear page.

OBIETTIVO

Il nostro obiettivo è migliorare l'intelligenza nel processo decisionale e nella governance delle città, sfruttando al tempo stesso le opportunità sociali e culturali. Promuovendo il coinvolgimento attivo dei cittadini nella raccolta dati e nel processo decisionale urbano attraverso gli Osservatori dei cittadini, creiamo una piattaforma affinché i cittadini possano contribuire attivamente al futuro delle loro città.

TITOLO DEL PROGETTO: GREENGAGE - COINVOLGERE I CITTADINI - MOBILITARE LA TECNOLOGIA - REALIZZARE UN GREEN DEAL

PROGRAMME: ORIZZONTE EUROPA

BANDO: HORIZON - CL6-2022-GOVERNANCE-01 GOVERNANCE INNOVATIVA, OSSERVAZIONI AMBIENTALI E SOLUZIONI DIGITALI A SUPPORTO DEL GREEN DEAL

COORDINATORE: AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY (AIT)

AVVIO: 01 GENNAIO 2023

DURATA: 3 ANNI

VISITA IL SITO DI PROGETTO
www.greengage-project.eu

PARTENARIATO

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

RAFFORZARE LA GOVERNANCE URBANA PROMUOVENDO LA CO-CREAZIONE BASATA SU PARTECIPAZIONE CITTADINA E LA RACCOLTA DATI

Sviluppare osservatori cittadini per integrare, convalidare e arricchire misurazioni autorevoli

www.greengage-project.eu

Figure 7: Promotional leaflet in Italian language: front page.

OBIETTIVO

- Aumentare la consapevolezza, l'interesse e l'impegno dei cittadini nei confronti delle questioni ambientali urbane
- Fornire metodi scientificamente validi e rigorosi per la comprensione da parte dei cittadini dei dati ambientali
- Promuovere e garantire tassi di accettazione e implementazione più ampi dei dati raccolti dai cittadini nel processo decisionale e politico
- Promuovere la co-creazione di soluzioni di dati per l'ambiente urbano
- Stabilire sinergie tra le città partner, con altri Osservatori Cittadini e istituzioni ambientali per scambiare le migliori pratiche, garantire la trasferibilità, l'adozione e la replicabilità delle esperienze di successo degli Osservatori Cittadini

OSSERVATORI CITTADINI

- Bristol (UK)
- Copenhagen (DK)
- North Brabant (NL)
- Turano (IT)
- Gerace (IT)

Concentrandosi sulla mobilità, sulla qualità dell'aria e sulla vita sana, i cittadini sono ispirati a osservare e co-creare le loro città percependo i loro ambienti urbani e sviluppando Osservatori Cittadini per integrare, convalidare e arricchire le informazioni esistenti in dati autorevoli detenuti dalle istituzioni e amministrazioni pubbliche.

Le informazioni basate sull'evidenza dei dati raccolti saranno utilizzate per una governance urbana intelligente, la valutazione e l'elaborazione delle politiche e del processo decisionale.

INSIEME DEGLI STRUMENTI GREENGAGE

GREENGAGE facilita le campagne multidisciplinari degli Osservatori Cittadini fornendo ad essi strumenti su misura per il monitoraggio ambientale: un insieme di tecnologie GREENGAGE.

Questo "insieme" di tecnologie è costituito da strumenti software e hardware, taluni dei partner del consorzio e che promuovono l'osservazione e la visualizzazione dei dati, l'elaborazione delle informazioni e l'apprendimento.

SENSORI PORTATILI

APP MOBILE

COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENT

SOLUZIONI DI VISUALIZZAZIONE

GEOSPAZIALE SOLUZIONI

SEGUICI!

- [linkedin.com/company/greengage-project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/greengage-project)
- @ GREENGAGE_EU
- @ GREENGAGE-project

Figure 8: Promotional leaflet in Italian language: rear page.

MISSIE

Om stedelijke besluitvorming en bestuur slimmer te maken, door sociale en culturele kansen te benutten om de betrekking van actieve burgers bij data vergaring en stedelijke besluitvorming aan de hand van Burgers Observatoria te bevorderen.

PROJECT TITLE: GREENGAGE - ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

PROGRAMMA: HORIZON EUROPE

CALL: HORIZON-CL4-2022-GOVERNANCE-01
INNOVATIVE GOVERNANCE, ENVIRONMENTAL OBSERVATIONS AND DIGITAL SOLUTIONS IN SUPPORT OF THE GREEN DEAL

COÖRDINATOR: AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY

START DATUM: 01 JANUARY 2023

DUUR: 3 YEARS

NEEM ONLINE CONTACT OP
www.greengage-project.eu

PARTNERS

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

VERSTERKEN VAN STEDELIJK BESTUUR DOOR HET BEVORDEREN VAN BURGER-GESTUURDE COCREATIE EN PUBLIEKSRAADPLEGING

GREENGAGE Observatoria ontwikkelen om bestuursmaatregelen te onderbouwen, valideren, en versterken

www.greengage-project.eu

Figure 9: Promotional leaflet in Dutch language: front page.

Figure 10: Promotional leaflet in Dutch language: rear page.

3.3 GREENGAGE Observatories Factsheet

Digital A4 factsheet booklet introducing GREENGAGE Innovation Pilots and their Observatories (Figure 11 and Figure 12) offers concise and comprehensive information on core aspects behind each of the pilots. The booklet is provided as a PDF document.

The booklet starts with the description of the innovation pilots, their general position marked on the map of Europe, and their role in the GREENGAGE project, specifically focusing on their aim to promote co-created Citizen Observatories as a part of a participatory governance process. Each following page is dedicated to a specific pilot city, offering a snapshot of key information such as the pilot's geographical location, its scale (i.e., a neighbourhood, a region, or a rural community), its vision, the existing data gaps, the identified use cases, and the considered technologies from the GREENGAGE repertoire.

The layout of the factsheet booklet features a clean and modern design, with a consistent GREENGAGE colour scheme, typography, and infographic elements. The booklet incorporates a reader-friendly structure, allowing readers to swiftly access relevant information about each pilot's unique requirements and needs.

The factsheet booklet serves as a valuable resource that effectively communicates the aims and challenges addressed in each pilot within the GREENGAGE project.

Revised design: The second version of the factsheet booklet addressed and corrected several wording errors and revised the individual pilots' information.

GREENGAGE
ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

STRENGTHENING URBAN GOVERNANCE BY PROMOTING CITIZEN-BASED CO-CREATION AND CROWD-SOURCING

Developing GREENGAGE Observatories towards complementing, validating and enriching authoritative measurements

www.greengage-project.eu

Funded by the European Union | UK Research and Innovation | Partnership

GREENGAGE
ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

CITIZEN OBSERVATORIES

INNOVATION PILOTS

GREENGAGE Innovation Pilots aim to promote co-created Citizen Observatories as part of a participatory governance process. They demonstrate how top-down urban planning processes can actively inform/mediate novel bottom-up processes of multi-stakeholder engagement.

The Innovation Pilots respond to the GREENGAGE mission to define and deliver Citizen Observatories as integral components of decision-making processes that address current urban and regional planning challenges of climate mitigation and adaptation as well as healthy cities.

The five GREENGAGE Observatories will be co-designed and fully demonstrated in Bristol (United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano (Italy), Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (The Netherlands).

Funded by the European Union | UK Research and Innovation | Partnership

GREENGAGE
ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

CITIZEN OBSERVATORIES

BRISTOL, UK

NEIGHBOURHOOD

VISION

The vision of Bristol City Council for the Liveable Neighbourhoods program is to empower local communities in transforming their neighbourhoods into safer, healthier, and more inclusive spaces.

DATA GAPS

- Granular understanding of street use
- Sensorial data (air quality) in target areas
- Perceptions/auto detection (safety, attractiveness, etc.) regarding different areas and quality of journey

USE CASES

- Impact of road closures on mobility patterns (journey quality)
- Identification of safety / threat levels
- Identification of mobility patterns for evaluation of urban accessibility
- Air quality / Environment monitoring

TECHNOLOGIES

PORTABLE SENSORS | MOBILE APPS | COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENT | VISUALIZATION DASHBOARDS | GEOSPATIAL SOLUTIONS

Funded by the European Union | UK Research and Innovation | Partnership

GREENGAGE
ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

CITIZEN OBSERVATORIES

COPENHAGEN, DK

NEIGHBOURHOOD

VISION

The vision of Copenhagen neighbourhood Bredst is to leverage crowdsourced data in local democratic dialogues towards creating a climate-positive neighbourhood with improved urban living conditions.

DATA GAPS

- Dynamic data on citizens' use of the neighbourhood and their movement patterns
- Perceptions detection (safety, attractiveness) regarding different public areas
- Air pollution data of frequently used public spaces
- Commuters' exposure to air pollution during commute

USE CASES

- Participatory environment monitoring
- Analysis of citizens' usage of public spaces and determine safety and attractiveness of public spaces

TECHNOLOGIES

PORTABLE SENSORS | MOBILE APPS | COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENT | VISUALIZATION DASHBOARDS | GEOSPATIAL SOLUTIONS

Funded by the European Union | UK Research and Innovation | Partnership

Figure 11: Citizen Observatories Factsheet Booklet: pages 1 - 4 of the PDF booklet.

GREENGAGE
ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

CITIZEN OBSERVATORIES

NORTH BRABANT, NL
PROVINCE

VISION
 The vision of the province of North Brabant is to address challenges of urbanization, traffic safety, health, inclusivity, economic, and energy issues, with a shift towards sustainable traffic and transport.

DATA GAPS

- Real-time GPS data of mobility patterns, chosen modal ty, function of trip
- Origin-destination and routing data for travel patterns (travel diary)
- Survey data on citizen experience of public transport
- Pressure points for short movements

USE CASES

- Visualization and analysis of multimodal travel patterns
- Identification of deterrents for bicycle usage, such as physical obstacles and other structural barriers

TECHNOLOGIES

PORTABLE SENSORS MOBILE APPS COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENT VISUALIZATION DASHBOARDS GEOSPATIAL SOLUTIONS

Funded by the European Union UK Research and Innovation Partnership

GREENGAGE
ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

CITIZEN OBSERVATORIES

TURANO, IT
RURAL COMMUNITY

VISION
 The vision of Turano is to tackle road infrastructure issues and progressive rural depopulation by identifying effective strategies for revitalization and improved mobility based on citizens' preferences.

DATA GAPS

- Dynamic data on traffic flows and mobility modes
- Air pollution data with focus on emission sources and pollution levels
- Data on road infrastructure conditions and accessibility

USE CASES

- Analysis of mobility patterns to determine accessibility to local amenities
- Analysis of citizens' usage of public spaces and determine attractiveness and conditions of public spaces and road infrastructure
- Participatory environment monitoring

TECHNOLOGIES

PORTABLE SENSORS MOBILE APPS COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENT VISUALIZATION DASHBOARDS GEOSPATIAL SOLUTIONS

Funded by the European Union UK Research and Innovation Partnership

GREENGAGE
ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

CITIZEN OBSERVATORIES

GERACE, IT
RURAL COMMUNITY

VISION
 The vision of Gerace is to tackle road infrastructure issues and progressive rural depopulation by identifying effective strategies for revitalization and improved mobility based on citizens' preferences.

DATA GAPS

- Dynamic data on traffic flows and mobility modes
- Air pollution data with focus on emission sources and pollution levels
- Data on road infrastructure conditions and accessibility

USE CASES

- Analysis of mobility patterns to determine accessibility to local amenities
- Analysis of citizens' usage of public spaces and determine attractiveness and conditions of public spaces and road infrastructure
- Participatory environment monitoring

TECHNOLOGIES

PORTABLE SENSORS MOBILE APPS COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENT VISUALIZATION DASHBOARDS GEOSPATIAL SOLUTIONS

Funded by the European Union UK Research and Innovation Partnership

GREENGAGE
ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

PARTNERS

AIT SUSHI DEV
 DIGITAL SUNRAY Breda University
 MILJOPUNKT AMAGER Deusto
 Provincie Noord-Brabant
 MOONDIAL gisat
 h2opu IRWE
 vrvis ibercivis
 KWMC
 MindEarth

Funded by the European Union UK Research and Innovation Partnership

Figure 12: Citizen Observatories Factsheet Booklet: pages 5 - 8 of the PDF booklet.

3.4 Roll-Up Banner

The roll-up banner summarizes the essential information about the project (Figure 13). The design prominently features the logo of the GREENGAGE project and a clear map marking the locations of Innovation Pilots involved. Core project goals are highlighted for quick reference, alongside a dedicated QR code and a web link directing the audience to the project's contact page for further engagement and inquiries. The layout balances visuals and text, ensuring easy readability and immediate impact at events and conferences. The design is also available in Italian and Dutch languages (Figure 14 and Figure 15).

STRENGTHENING URBAN GOVERNANCE BY PROMOTING CITIZEN-BASED CO-CREATION AND CROWD-SOURCING

17 PARTNERS FROM EU & UK **5** INNOVATION PILOTS **>15** THEMATIC CO-EXPLORATIONS

 Empowering Local Communities to Actively Contribute to the Future of Their Cities

 Democratizing Local Policy-Making & Innovation

 Complementing Existing Environmental Data Repositories

GET IN TOUCH

 @greengage-project
 @GREENGAGE_EU
 contact@greengage-project.eu

 greengage-project.eu

Figure 13: Promotional roll-up banner.

Rafforzare la governance urbana promuovendo la co-creazione e la collaborazione partecipativa dei cittadini

17

PARTNER DELL'UE E DEL REGNO UNITO

5

AREE PILOTA INNOVATIVE

>15

CO-ESPLORAZIONI TEMATICHE

 Coinvolgere le comunità locali per contribuire a plasmare il futuro delle loro città

 Rendere la formulazione delle politiche e l'innovazione locali accessibili a tutti

 Integrare i Dati Ambientali Preesistenti

PER RESTARE IN CONTATTO

 @greengage-project
 @GREENGAGE_EU
 contact@greengage-project.eu

 greengage-project.eu

Figure 14: Promotional roll-up banner in Italian language.

VERSTERKEN VAN STEDELIJK BESTUUR DOOR HET BEVORDEREN VAN BURGER-GESTUURDE COCREATIE EN PUBLIEKSRAADPLEGING

17

**PARTNERS
UIT EU & VK**

5

**INNOVATIE
PILOTS**

>15

**THEMATISCHE
CO-VERKENNING**

**Versterken van lokale gemeenschappen
in het actief bijdragen aan de toekomst
van hun steden**

**Lokale beleidsvorming en
innovatie democratiseren**

**Bestaande omgevingsdata
opslag uitbreiden**

NEEM CONTACT

@greengage-project

@GREENGAGE_EU

contact@greengage-project.eu

greengage-project.eu

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Project funded by
the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Netherlands

Figure 15: Promotional roll-up banner in Dutch language.

3.5 T-Shirt Design

The T-shirt design was specifically created for use during project-organized Ideathons and Datathons, serving as a visual identifier that reinforces the GREENGAGE brand and highlights its funding support. The design prominently features the GREENGAGE logo and relevant funding information to ensure clear project visibility. To foster a sense of community and facilitate easy identification during events, two distinct T-shirt colours were used: one designated for project partners and another for participants. Accordingly, two colour schemes - black and white - were developed to reflect these roles (Figure 16: T-shirt design that features the GREENGAGE logo and relevant funding information.).

Figure 16: T-shirt design that features the GREENGAGE logo and relevant funding information.